

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES, THEIR ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS.

Akbarkhanov Sarvarkhan Saidumarkhan ogli

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11079309>

Abstract. *this article presents information on the importance of digital technologies in improving the effectiveness of foreign languages in educational institutions, the role of innovative pedagogical technologies and approaches for developing the quality of foreign language in our education system.*

Keywords: *computer technology, distance learning, innovative pedagogical technologies, interactive methods.*

Introduction:

As we all know, language is a means of interaction, communication, a king of thought. For the peoples of the world, their native language is their invaluable value, the pride of the nation. Language is also the consciousness and memory of the nation, its psyche, spiritual and cultural image, national values, its past. The role of language in the development of a nation, state, society is very important, extremely necessary and relevant. As the nation, state, society progress, his love and attention to the language will also increase. Progress in social life determines progress in language.

Knowledge of a foreign language has become a fundamental condition in finding its place in life. Since we do not know at least one foreign language other than our native language, it is still possible not to think about having a high-income job around the world, sharing experiences, increasing knowledge.

In the years of independence, more than 50,000 Foreign Language teachers were trained in our country. In terms of attention to language learning in our country, unprecedented work has been carried out in the next 5-10 years, bringing it to the level of politics, and several decisions and decrees on the study of foreign languages have been developed, in particular, a video Assembly dedicated to improving the system of learning foreign languages was held under the presidency of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. It was noted at the meeting that from 2021, Foreign Language teachers will be required to have a national and international certificate. Now, instead of constant traditional lesson methods, the organization of lesson processes based on interactive methods using new Information Communication Technologies (ICT) has been established [1, 1].

Development of innovative methods of teaching foreign languages at the Uzbekistan State University of world languages under the Ministry of higher and secondary special education of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of the 4 state units of the Republican scientific and practical Center, a network qualification structure for the dual certification system was established in cooperation with prestigious centers for advanced training in foreign.

By the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022, funds were allocated from the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the purchase of modern educational and scientific literature, textbooks and educational manuals, international tests and related permits and licenses for their introduction, which are published in foreign countries in the teaching of foreign languages [2,1].

According to the deputy of the Legislative Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan Nadir Tilavoldiyev, today a number of foreign teachers are involved in Uzbekistan's schools in order to improve the quality of education and effectively use advanced experience in this. The reference books of 551 foreign English language specialists from 22 foreign countries have now been studied and an interview process has been organized with 236 of these, with recruitment proposals sent to 185 foreign English language specialists.

Modern teaching technologies are a complex integral (whole, continuous) system, in which the skills and competencies established on the basis of educational goals are reflected by students as a competent orderly set of elements of pedagogical activity aimed at mastering theoretical knowledge, educating certain spiritual and moral qualities in them.

The concept of "technology" came to the garden with information about 60 years of American and Western education. B. Kino, J. Coroll, P. Ya.Galperin, W. I. Davydov, N. A. Menchinskaya, Z. I. Kalmykova, L. I. Zankov technologies are popular.

Illuminates one side of T. A. Ballo's technology, the instructional approach to reading. In others, the problematic structure of training or Training, programmed either through a computer, stands out.

L. V. Zankov, T. Ya. Galperin, W. I. Davidov's research focuses on holistic technologies of primary education [5,72].

One of the important requirements for the organization of modern education is to record high rates in a short period of time, without excessive mental and physical exertion.

Pedagogical technology in its essence is subjective in nature, that is, each educator must organize the process of education and upbringing based on his capabilities, professional skills. Today, in a number of developed countries, great experience has been accumulated in the application of innovative pedagogical technologies that increase the educational and creative activity of students and guarantee the effectiveness of the educational and educational process, and the methods that make up the foundations of this experience are referred to as "**interactive methods**".

Programmed teaching appeared at the beginning of the 50s of the 20th century. It is associated with the name of the American psychologist B. Skinner. He recommended the construction and control of materials on the basis of a regular program of part-by-part information transmission, in increasing the efficiency of material appropriation management.

N. Crowder has developed a branched bench, in which, according to the results of control, learners are recommended materials of different types for independent work.

G. K. Selevko gives the following definition to programmed teaching, i.e., programmed teaching means teaching equipment (**ECM {electronic computing machines}, programmed textbook, and etc.**) to understand the management of the appropriation of programmed learning material. The programmed learning material will consist of a series of relatively non-large learning information that is given in a certain logical consistency [4,56]

Innovative technologies in the teaching of foreign languages are of great importance in educational institutions. These technologies help to master the learning process, creating interesting and effective teaching opportunities for students. For the following reasons, these technologies are important:

1. Making learning fun and motivational: innovative technologies provide students with interactive lessons, acquired activities, and gameplay elements to make the learning process more interesting and motivating. This increases the interest and firm confidence of the students.

2. Personalized learning: innovative technologies that help students provide personalized learning directions. This makes it possible to provide mastered programming and Educational Directions for each student.

3. Learning enhancement: technologies such as Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and artificial intelligence (AI) help students enhance learning and drive the niche of realistic practices. They provide opportunities for students to implement practices and make the learning process more efficient.

4. Expanding areas of application for teachers: innovative technologies help teachers create areas of extended application. They are used in the preparation of automated lessons, monitoring the progress of students, and in the study of personalized educational directions.

5. Freedom: Mobile Apps and online platforms provide freedom for readers. This ensures that students learn more comfortably and quickly.

6. Global dialogue and cooperation: innovative technologies in the study of foreign languages play an important role in creating global dialogue and cooperation for students in different nations. This allows students to share their thoughts with other language learners around the world and observe change.

Conclusion.

In general, the popularization of foreign language learning has become one of the priority goals in today's educational system. The effect of this is now evident in the dramatic increase in interest in language learning among young people across the country. These efforts in the field of Education, solving any issues faced in the study and teaching of foreign languages, make a significant contribution to raising the prestige of Science, Education and development of our homeland on a global scale.

REFERENCES

1. 2021-yil 19-maydagi “Xorijiy tillarni o’rganishni ommalashtirishni samarali tashkil etish chora-tadbirlari to’g’risida”gi O’zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar mahkamasining № 312 – son qarori
2. 2022-yil 19-yanvardagi “Xorijiy tillarni o’rganishni takomillashtirish bo’yicha qo’shimcha chora-tadbirlar to’g’risida”gi O’zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar mahkamasining № 34 – son qarori
3. O’zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlis Qonuchilik palatasining <https://parliament.gov.uz> sayti.
4. Azizkhodjayeva N. N. Pedagogik texnologiyalar va pedagogik mahorat. O’quv qo’llanma. - T.: O’zbekiston Yozuvchilar uyushmasi Adabiyot jamg’armasi nashriyoti. 2006. –56p.
5. O’. Q. Tolipova, M. Usmonboyeva. Pedagogik texnologiyalarning tatbiqiy asoslari. O’quv qo’llanma. – Toshkent: O’zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar akademiyasi “Fan” nashriyoti. 2006. –72p.
6. <file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/til-o-rganishda-zamonaviy-texnologiyalarning-o-rni.pdf>
7. [file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/xorijiy-tillarni-o-rganishda-zamonaviy-texnologiyalarning-o-rni-va-ahamiyati%20\(1\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/xorijiy-tillarni-o-rganishda-zamonaviy-texnologiyalarning-o-rni-va-ahamiyati%20(1).pdf)